

A Guide to the Erasmus Mundus Scholarship

Zain Ul Abideen

EMJM – Astrophysics and Space Science

Greetings everyone! My name is Zain Ul Abideen, and I graduated from the Space Science program in 2024 from the Institute of Space Technology, Islamabad, Pakistan. I have been selected in the Erasmus Mundus Joint Master program in Astrophysics and Space Science (EMJM-MASS), which is fully-funded by the European Union. I am writing this guide specifically for my juniors, and generally for anyone who plans on applying to the Erasmus Mundus scholarship. This guide is based upon my experiences in applying to the EMJM-MASS program, but the general ideas can be extrapolated to any other EMJM program. Contrary to popular belief, the crafting of your application doesn't start a few weeks or months before the program deadline, but years. **If you want to get selected for the scholarship, you have to distinguish yourself from the crowd.** You must have accomplished at least one thing that others have not. This could be landing a prestigious internship, scoring a funding from a reputable organization, publishing an article with a reputed company, or something similar. You have to sell yourself to the admissions committee by giving them reasons to choose you over everyone else. If you cannot distinguish yourself from your peers, then you will probably not be selected. In my case, I was one of the few students in the history of my department to have multiple research publications in international peer-reviewed journals at the undergraduate level. In addition to that, I was also a cum laude graduate and a gold-medalist. Furthermore, for reporting a bug in a nuclear reaction simulation code, I received a letter of appreciation from a senior official at the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), something I also mentioned in my application. Now many of you would ask what if it's too late? What should a person who couldn't accomplish anything distinctive during their degree do? Well, first of all, that person should not even spend his time applying for scholarships because he or she is not going to get selected. Unfortunately in this age, the competition is just too high. That person should focus on achieving something distinctive through work experience, which is the logical next step. Alongside the work experience, that person should also enroll in a local reputed university for masters, and give it all they got. If they are able to achieve something that distinguishes them from the crowd during their masters, they would have no problem securing a fully-funded PhD position abroad. In my opinion, what that person should absolutely not do is waste their time thinking they will fit in somewhere in some scholarship, because they probably won't. For any future correspondence, you can write me an email at dominuszain@gmail.com, but I might take some time to respond. You can poke me if I haven't responded in a few weeks. I wish best of luck to all future applicants.

How do I craft a winning CV?

Before you write anything in your CV file, you must thoroughly read the website of the program you are applying to. I cannot stress this enough, your CV should be completely inline with the requirements specified on your program website, otherwise you are not getting selected. Additionally, if you plan on applying to multiple EMJM programs, you must craft CVs for each of them separately, inline with their respective requirements. I myself read every single page of www.master-mass.eu so many times that I have the contents memorized now. Crucial things like whether the EMJM program you are interested in applying is offering fully-funded scholarships for this intake or not, are written on the website. So, to start, you should read and understand the contents on the website so many times that in situations you might forget your name, you never forget the stuff on the web-pages. After that, you can start work on crafting your CV. Many EMJM programs require applicants to use the Europass format for the CV. If that is the case then you can sign up on the Europass website and start crafting your CV there. Otherwise, any professional format should be good enough. For my case, nowhere on the EMJM-MASS website was it specified that I had to use a Europass format for my CV, so I used a Word template that is usually used by the US applicants. At the end of the day, if there is no compulsion, the choice of CV template comes down to personal preferences. Looking back, if I were to craft my CV now, I would probably use a LaTeX template that goes by the name of “Jake’s CV”. It is open-source, and available on GitHub. Now, coming to the specifics of the CV, it must have standard margins, should follow standard font and size, and must have the standard headings. What should not be standard is the stuff under the headings. My CV structure went like this. I had my name on the top, and just under my name, I had my contact information. The first heading was an “about me” section. It should not exceed 3 lines at any cost. The very next section after this must be about your education. You should never mention any qualifications, like O/A levels, that came before your undergraduate education throughout the CV and even the motivation letter. If you have just graduated with a bachelor’s degree, you should mention that, along with your CGPA. The way you mention these things must be pleasing to the eyes. One thing that most students forget to mention under this heading is relevant courses. If I am a Space Science graduate, applying to an astrophysics program, the admissions committee doesn’t know what the curriculum of my program covers. I must mention some core and elective courses that define what my degree is all about. After this section, It really depends upon you and the program you are applying to. The nice to have sections include research and internships, research publications, honors and awards, work experience, voluntary activities, coding projects, and so on. A thing to keep in mind is that your CV must never exceed two full pages at most. No matter if you discovered new laws of physics in your undergraduate years, your CV can always be condensed to two full pages. Another thing on which I will stress here as well as in the motivation letter section is redundancy. Every single word must add new information to your CV. You must remember that English is at most a second language to the members of the admissions committee, so don’t use any words that require Googling to understand. Your CV must never contain anything that is not relevant to the program you are applying to. For example, let’s say I am applying to an astrophysics program, and I have done the following volunteer works: ran a charity, tutored under-privileged

students, served as the head of publication department at a society, and helped organize the world space week. Many students would be compelled to mention all of them on their CV to each program application, but that is a grave mistake. **If you make the admissions committee feel, at any moment, that you have wasted their time in any way, your whole application is done and dusted.** For the astrophysics program, the charity work is completely irrelevant, but others can be made relevant. Regarding your tutoring, if it involves teaching astrophysics or space sciences, then its relevant. Otherwise, don't mention it. Regarding the publications department at a society, if the society is related to astrophysics or space in general, then it's relevant otherwise it's not. Finally, regarding the world space week one, it will always be relevant for the astrophysics program. I hope I have conveyed how relevancy plays a role in shaping your application for each program. The very last thing I would mention in this section is that the CV must not be wordy, and be pleasing to the eyes. The language used in the CV must be formal and grammatically sound, and the formatting must be consistent. If you put a full-stop at the end of bullet points, then you must put it everywhere. If you don't, then don't put it anywhere. If I were to condense everything I have said in this section so far, I would say that just make a really professional CV in accordance with the stuff mentioned on the program website.

How do I write a motivation letter?

The part of your application on which you must spend most of your time is the motivation letter. A motivation letter can literally make or break your application. The first thing I would say is that, the people on the other side who are reviewing your application are not fools. So don't give them anything to laugh about as any attempts on emotional manipulation would be utterly useless. **The EMJM programs are funded by merit-based scholarships, so your motivation letter must be based upon what you have achieved given your situation, and not on your situation itself.** There are a million ways of writing a motivation letter, and most of them are sound. I would list some things that are common in all of them, but this is not a guide on how to write motivation letters in general, but rather what worked for me. All good motivation letters, first of all, use grammatically sound language (so use something like Grammarly often), and secondly, use hooks. A hook is something that glues the reader to your letter. You must have hooks at least at the start of your motivation letter, and ideally, in every paragraph. A word of caution to not overdo things, as at the end of the day, your letter must not sound like it was written by a retard (my first couple of drafts were like that). Similar to the CV, your motivation letter must not cross the two page limit in any way. Mine was one page only, and it was good enough to land me a fully-funded offer. Also similar to the CV case, your motivation letter must not have any redundancy, and must only be relevant to the program you are applying to. The redundancy here includes the stuff you mentioned in your CV. If you explained something in your CV, you must not write about it again in the motivation letter unless you have a really good reason to. For example, the stuff I discussed in my motivation letter, I only wrote a few words on them in my CV. My craft was such that the letter as well as the CV added new and relevant information on the same things. The structure of my motivation letter was as follows:

paragraph 1: [Hook], a little about why am I writing this letter and what motivated me to write this letter and apply to this specific program.

paragraph 2: The relevant volunteer work I did during my first years as an undergraduate student. I also mentioned, quantitatively, something I achieved which not everyone does.

paragraph 3: The research I did in my final years, the academic awards I got, the impact my work had, and another thing I achieved which not everybody does. I also had a [Hook] in here somewhere.

paragraph 4: The relevant skills I developed during my undergraduate degree. Yet another thing I did which not everyone can do, and what I am doing now to further enhance my skills. I had another minor [Hook] here in this paragraph.

paragraph 5: The details of why I am applying to this specific program. What motivates me? Why not study in my own country (don't be too honest)? If I am given the scholarship, what would I achieve? What are my future goals? and you know, stuff like this. In here, you have to demonstrate that you have done your research about this specific program. If it's appropriate, you can mention names of professors and what "specifically" you would like to work on with them. This should be the longest and the most thought out paragraph of your motivation letter. *This paragraph right here is the heart of your whole application, so don't mess this up.*

paragraph 6: Here you are going to conclude your letter. Just summarize everything briefly without being redundant, and end it in a nice way. You should study how "brother may I have some oats" ends (YouTube it). I also had a [Hook] in the last paragraph.

If I had to summarize everything in this section, I would say just write a well-structured motivation letter, where each paragraph has a distinct theme, focusing on your achievements, and not on your (poor) conditions. Do not be redundant in any way, and use hooks to capture the reader's attention.

Everything should be relevant and nothing should be redundant!

The infamous Italian visa process

Now, if you managed to secure a fully-funded offer, your next biggest hurdle would be getting a visa. For some countries, it's a piece of cake, while for others, it's harder than securing the scholarship itself. I can only talk about Italy, since that's where my first semester is. If your first country is not Italy, here is what you can do: contact your program seniors (email them, text them on LinkedIn etc), watch YouTube videos on the study visa process of your first country, and contact the same people for guidance who sent you the scholarship letter. You should also join the relevant Facebook and WhatsApp groups, and know that the European delegation in your country would assist you in the visa process, and never compare your visa process, as a fully-funded scholarship student, with self-funded ones. Coming back to Italy, the first thing you need to get done is attestations. Your Matric/Intermediate certificates (alternatively your O/A levels equivalence certificates) must be attested by IBCC. You should watch some YouTube videos on it, but most probably you are going to go to a courier office like TCS, and tell them you need your docs attested from IBCC, and then they are going to do the rest. In parallel, you should get your bachelor's degree and transcript attested from HEC (watch some YouTube videos). After you got your certificates and

degrees attested from IBCC and HEC, you need to get all of them apostilled from MOFA. Again, you can watch some YouTube videos on how to get docs apostilled. Next, you need to find out whether you need CIMEA or DOV (Google and YouTube them if you are hearing these words for the first time). Even if your university accepts both, I would still recommend you go with CIMEA since it is easier than DOV but costs more money. You can apply for the statements of comparability and verification on the CIMEA website, and watch a YouTube video for the process. You will only need to upload scanned copies of your bachelor's degree and transcript attested by HEC at least, and you will receive your certificates in a couple of weeks. After that, you need to do your pre-enrollment. Watch a YouTube video on how to do pre-enrollment on the university portal, and go through with it. Once you have submitted the pre-enrollment form, your host university would verify the uploaded stuff and upon confirmation, forward a summary to your respective Italian embassy or consulate. Once your pre-enrollment summary has been forwarded, you need to find the current Italian study visa checklist, and make sure you have the required documents. Some common ones include FRC, which you can get from your closest NADRA office, health insurance, which you will get from the project office, proof of accommodation (I will get to it in a while), and other usual stuff. Since you are selected on scholarship, your program project office would guide and assist you on each step on the process, so don't feel shy to write them an email. The process till here is really straight-forward, and now the hard part begins. The Italian visa appointments are rarer than gold in Pakistan. The biggest hurdle anyone applying to Italy faces is securing a visa appointment. Every year, as soon as the appointments open, they are booked within seconds by 'consultants' who use bots to fill in the forms and lock them in. They later sell these appointments to aspiring students for huge sums of money. I would like to believe this is not by design, but the fact remains, the Italian visa process is corrupted. Fortunately, as scholarship students, you won't have to deal with those 'consultants'. **The European delegation in Pakistan assists EMJM students in getting the visa appointment.** The most important thing is that the students who have Italy as their first country must band together. There is a Facebook page by the name of "Erasmus Mundus Association Pakistan" or something like that. Once you have the letter of nomination for the scholarship, you need to send it to the admin of that Facebook group, and he will add you to a private group with all of the selected students. There, you will find students in the same situation as you, and you guys can figure stuff out together. Now, regarding the proof of accommodation required for visa processing, you can make a cancelable booking somewhere like booking.com, attach and submit it with your visa application, and once you have your visa, you can cancel it. That's because those prices are really high, and you can later find cheaper accommodations once you have the visa. There are a lot of YouTube videos on how to make a free accommodation booking for visa purposes. As for the real accommodation, there is no easy way. You will have to join groups, contact people, and so on. Another thing you must keep in mind is that, although you are a fully-funded scholarship student, you will still need to take a sum of money with you that should be enough for a couple of months. You cannot receive the scholarship amount unless you have a European bank account on your name, and that takes like a month. Your total cost from your own pocket would be around a few thousand Euros, which you can take a loan from a family member, and once you start getting the scholarship, you can return it with ease within a couple of months. The rest of the process you will be able to

figure out on your own as you interact with your peers. You can always contact the project office of your program, and they will assist you in any way possible. If I had to summarize everything in this section, I would say get a loan if you are broke, connect with others in the same situation as you, and write lots and lots of emails to lots and lots of people. If scholarship students in the same boat band together, they can make it through. To end this guide on an encouraging note, I will say this. Every year, lots of students who have the same first country get selected, and all of them get their visas before the starting of their classes. The process is often tiring and stressful, but at the end of the day, everyone makes it. *If the sun has been rising from the east every single day in the past, then it's safe to assume that it will rise from the east tomorrow as well.*

Special thanks

I would like to thank my senior *Dilawaiz Saghir* (EMJM scholar in Planetary Geosciences) for the guidance she gave me for my application.

Appendix

ZAIN UL ABIDEEN
Islamabad, Pakistan • (+92) 313 5500681 • dominuszain@gmail.com

ABOUT ME

Final Year Project at the Department of Space Science Aug. 2023 – Jul. 2024

FORMAL EDUCATION

B.S. Space Science, Institute of Space Technology (CGPA: 3.51/4.00) Graduated Sep. 2024
Relevant Courses – Astronomy & Astrophysics, Modern Physics, Solar Physics, Quantum Mechanics.

RESEARCH EXPERIENCE

Final Year Project at the Department of Space Science Aug. 2023 – Jul. 2024

Internship at the Space Education Research Lab, NCGSA Jul. 2023 – Aug. 2023

COMPUTATIONAL SKILLS

PEER-REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS

RESEARCH IN PROGRESS

HONORS AND AWARDS

VOLUNTEER WORK

CERTIFICATIONS

CODING PROJECTS

Simulation of [Project Name] [Link]

Simulation of [Project Name] [Link]

Simulation of [Project Name] [Link]